

Thermal & Mechanical Design and Production of a Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism

*Emin Taner ELMAS¹

*¹ Assistant Professor Dr., Vocational School of Higher Education for Technical Sciences, Division of Motor Vehicles and Transportation Technologies, Department of Automotive Technology, Iğdır University, Turkey & Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences - Major Science Department of Bioengineering and Bio-Sciences, Iğdır University, Turkey
Iğdır University, 76000
Iğdır – TURKEY

*¹ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7290-2308>
+90 (0) 543 733 64 21
e.taner.elmas@igdir.edu.tr

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Abstract

In this article, “Thermal & Mechanical Design and Production of a Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism” is considered and explained.

The mechanical and thermal design of this “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism” is completely original, unique and belongs to the author of this article who is Emin Taner ELMAS. He and all the technical calculations of this project also realized by him develop the technical project drawings at the conclusion section of this article. There are also original photographs of the “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism” which is manufactured after the thermal and mechanical design works.

As it is known, granular solid materials are hygroscopic. When moisture transfers from the product to the air in the space between the granules, the humidity of the air will increase. This can cause condensation on the surface of the cold heat exchanger plates. Condensation on the plates will quickly lead to caking in the cooler. [16], [17], [18], [19]

The Cooling Machine for Granular Solids Cooler is designed for long term, reliable operation without the need for regular cleaning. To achieve this, the mechanism of condensation and product caking must be prevented. To prevent condensation the dewpoint of the air in the void space of the cooler needs to be lower than the temperature of the plate exchanger. [16], [17], [18], [19]

The dewpoint of the air in the heat exchanger changes relative to the temperature of the product. The relationship between dewpoint and temperature is governed by the critical relative humidity (CRH) of the cooling machine. Each cooling machine has a unique CRH characteristic. [16], [17], [18], [19]

As the granular solids cools when it passes through the exchanger, the dewpoint lowers. The relationship between product temperature, dewpoint and water temperature is shown on the graphs of article. These graphs demonstrates the importance of counter-current water flow to avoid caking and optimize energy efficiency. Understanding the science behind granular solid cooling enables the heat exchangers to be customized for each type of cooling machine and

any ambient conditions. [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31]

Keywords

Energy, Energy Transfer, Fluid Mechanics, Thermodynamics, Heat Transfer, Mathematics, Cooling, Cooling Machine, Mechanical Engineering, Dew Point, Temperature, Relative Humidity, Thermoplate.

Introduction

A general perspective of the mentioned “Cooling Machine for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid -Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism” is shown in Figure 1. [16], [17], [18], [19]

As the granular solids cools when it passes through the exchanger, the dewpoint lowers. The relationship between product temperature, dewpoint and water temperature is shown on the below graph. This graph demonstrates the importance of counter-current water flow to avoid caking and optimize energy efficiency. Understanding the science behind granular solid cooling enables the heat exchangers to be customized for each type of cooling machine and any ambient conditions See Figure 2. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Figure 1 A general perspective of the mentioned “Cooling Machine for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Figure 2 The relationship between product temperature, dewpoint and water temperature. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Figure 3 Moisture transfer of granular solid material. [16], [17], [18], [19]

The condensation process, the moisture transfer of granular solid material and the caking with cooled surface are shown in Figure 3. The general schematic of “Cooling Machine for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism” is shown Figure 4. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Figure 4 General schematic of “Cooling Machine for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”. [16], [17], [18], [19]
 [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31]

Method, Findings and Discussion

The granular cooling machine guarantees highly efficient thermal performance and ongoing, reliable operation. [16], [17], [18], [19]

The cooling machine is custom designed taking into account:

- Type of granular solid
- Required thermal performance
- Local ambient conditions
- Selection of optimum water temperatures
- Selection of optimum purge air flow rate and dewpoint to prevent condensation

Water Temperature Control Module:

The Water Temperature Control Module (WTCM), open or closed loop, controls the cooling water temperatures and water flow rate through the cooling machine. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Key Features:

- Open loop operates strictly on plant cooling water with a recirculation circuit for water temperature control
- Closed loop (used in high chloride cooling water and other poor water quality sources), operates on a secondary self-contained water loop with a plate exchanger isolating the granular solid cooling machine from the primary plant cooling water supply
- Both open and closed loop designs include a start-up heater to preheat the plates

- Pumps can be standalone or standby depending on customer requirements
- Skid mounted

Chiller / Dry Cooler System – Optimized to Reduce Energy Cost:

If plant water is not available or is too warm to meet process requirements, the WTCM may include a dry cooler and/or a chiller. This combined system will be optimized so that the chiller will only operate during summer months. The remainder of the year the system will operate solely with dry coolers to save energy costs. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Purge Air Module:

The Purge Air Module provides purge air to the Cooling Machine. Where possible, ambient air is used, reducing operating costs and minimizing capital costs. If conditioned air is required, due to process requirements or ambient conditions an air dehumidification system is used to reduce the air dewpoint. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Advantages compared to Air Cooling (Rotary or Fluid Bed):

- Efficient cooling without emissions
- Gentle handling (low velocity ~ 13mm/sec)
- Low energy consumption
- Low maintenance
- Compact design
- Simple system
- Reliable operation

Principle of Operation: Combines the science of mass flow with indirect heat transfer as shown in Figure 5. [16], [17], [18], [19]

The operation principle is itemized as below:

- 1- Product flows slowly by gravity between water cooled plates
- 2- Product flows in uniform velocity mass flow
- 3- Water flows counter-current inside plates

Figure 5 of Mass flow with indirect heat transfer mechanism. [16], [17], [18], [19]

What causes caking: (As shown in Figure 6):

Figure 6 Caking process. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Preventing Caking Mechanism: (As shown in Figure 7):

Figure 7 Preventing caking mechanism. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Thermoplate Design:

- Fully Laser Welded Plates (Carbon Steel, SS304L, SS316L, SS2205, Titanium etc.) • Inflated to 40 bar
- Design to ASME, PED etc.
- Internal passes create turbulent flow for even thermal conductivity and avoid sediment build up

Higher Equivalent Surface Area:

Plates – Heat Transfer Surface Area and Tubes – Heat Transfer Surface Area are mentioned in Figure 8 and Figure 9, respectively. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Figure 8 Plates – Heat Transfer Surface Area – 60 m^2 per 1 m^3 of volume. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Figure 9 Tubes – Heat Transfer Surface Area – 20 m^2 per per 1 m^3 of volume. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Thermal Modelling:

Need accurate thermal modeling to predict thermal performance. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Product Side:

Temperatures (in/out)

Specific heat

Thermal Conductivity

Bulk density

Fluid side:

Temperatures (in/out)

Specific heat

Viscosity

Equipment geometry:

Number of banks

Plate spacing

Water configuration (series/parallel)

Laboratory Testing:

Bulk density

Thermal conductivity

Specific heat

Angle of repose

Particle size distribution

Flowability

Shear cell

Design to ensure reliable, long term operation:

Challenges cooling granular solids as follows (shown in Figure 10): [16], [17], [18], [19]

- Granular solids are hygroscopic & contain a small percentage of moisture

- Moisture migrates from the prill or granule to air in void space

- If the dewpoint of the air in the void space is above the exchanger plate temperature, condensation will occur

- This leads to the scaling and plugging mechanism

- Leading to lost production time due to more regular cleaning

Figure 10 Condensation on thermoplates. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Design to ensure no Scaling or Plugging (As shown in Figure 11):

- Moisture migration is defined by the product Critical Relative Humidity Curve (CRH curve).
- The CRH curve is unique for each type of cooling machine
- Detailed modeling predicts the dewpoint
- Correct selection of water temperature ensures that there will be no condensation on the plates
- Addition of a low volume of purge air improves the efficiency

Figure 11 Relationship between Relative Humidity and Temperature. [16], [17], [18], [19]

The Secret to Long Term Operating Performance - Ensuring Water Temperature is above the Dew Point (As shown in Figure 12, Figure 13, Figure 14 and Figure 15):

Figure 12 Ensuring Water Temperature is above the Dew Point. [16], [17], [18], [19]
The CRH Curves: (As shown Figure 13):

Figure 13 Relationship between CRH and Temperature. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Figure 14 CRH – Urea Prills. [16], [17], [18], [19]

CRH Curves for Different Products

Figure 15 CRH Curves for different products. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Air Injection to Improve Efficiency:

Combination of water temperatures and air injection prevents caking as shown in Figure 16. [16], [17], [18], [19]

- Design based on CRH of cooling machine type
- Design models dew point through exchanger
- Select optimum water temperature profile to avoid condensation and efficient heat transfer
- Select optimum purge air flowrate & dewpoint

Graph of dewpoint & water temperatures in cooler

Figure 16 Combination of water temperatures and air injection prevents caking. [16], [17], [18], [19]

The Complete System (As shown in Figure 17):

- High Efficiency multi-bank exchanger
- Water Temperature Control Module to provide correct water temperatures
- Air Module to provide purge air at correct dewpoint
- Comprehensive instrumentation and control package

Figure 17 The complete cooling system. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Test Set-Up: (As shown in Figure 18):

Figure 18 Test set-up for the complete cooling machine. [16], [17], [18], [19]

Test Set-up:

- Double Bank Exchanger
- Controlled Cooling Water Temperatures
- Purge Air system
- Demonstrate long term run capability without caking

Typical Granular Solid Cooling Machine: (As shown in Figure 19 and Figure 20):

Figure 19 Typical Granular Solid Cooling Machine. [16], [17], [18], [19]

- **Product Flowrate** :100 t/h
- **Product Size** :1 – 4 mm
- **Product Temperature in** :85 °C
- **Required Product Temp. out:** < 50°C
- **Cooling Water** : Cooling Tower at 28°C
- **Purge Air** : Required

Figure 20 Typical Granular Solid Cooling Machine. [16], [17], [18], [19]
 [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19],
 [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31]

Conclusion

The mechanical and thermal design of this “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism” is completely original, unique and belongs to the author of this article who is Emin Taner ELMAS. He and all the technical calculations of this project also realized by him develop the technical project drawings at the conclusion section of this article. There are also original photographs of the “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism” which is manufactured after the thermal and mechanical design works. [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31]

Figure 21, Figure 22 and Figure 23 give the technical project drawings of “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism” developed after the mechanical and thermal design of complete unit. Figure 24 shows the technical details of the thermoplates used for the heat exchanger unit of “Cooling Machine for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid Energy Transfer Mechanism”. [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31]

Figure 25, 26 and 27 show the mechanical parts used for “Cooling Machine for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”. [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31]

Figure 22 The technical project drawings of “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism” developed after the mechanical and thermal design of complete unit.

Figure 23 The technical project drawings of “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism” developed after the mechanical and thermal design of complete unit.

Figure 24 The technical details of the thermoplates used for the heat exchanger unit of “Cooling Machine for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 25 The mechanical parts used for “Cooling Machine for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 26 The mechanical parts used for “Cooling Machine for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 27 The mechanical parts used for “Cooling Machine for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid -Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 28 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 29 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 30 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 31 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 32 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 33 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 34 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 35 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 36 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 37 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 38 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 39 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 40 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 41 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 42 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 43 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 44 “Cooling Machine Heat Exchanger with Thermoplates for Granular Solids Using the Solid-Liquid-Gas Energy Transfer Mechanism”.

Figure 45 Plates which are used to manufacture heat exchanger thermoplates.

Figure 46 Plates which are used to manufacture heat exchanger thermoplates.

Figure 47 Thermoplates used for Heat Exchanger of Cooling Machine.

Figure 48 Thermoplates used for Heat Exchanger of Cooling Machine.

Figure 49 Thermoplates used for Heat Exchanger of Cooling Machine.

Figure 50 Thermoplates used for Heat Exchanger of Cooling Machine.

Figure 51 Thermoplate bundles used for Heat Exchanger of Cooling Machine.

Figure 52 Thermoplate bundles used for Heat Exchanger of Cooling Machine.

[1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31]

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